

Base Catalysed Rearrangements of oxy-Cope Systems[†]

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I consider it a great honour to be invited by the Indian Chemical Society to deliver the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Lecture, 1981. Acharya Ray was a man of many parts—chemist, industrial entrepreneur, social reformer keenly interested in the improvement of village life, a great sanskrit scholar and a prolific writer. Though born of a well-to-do family, he led a life of simple habit and high thinking as enjoined by our *Sastras*. The Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works founded by him in 1892 is a monument to his vision. Over his long career as a teacher of chemistry and research chemist, he trained and inspired a large number of chemists who went forth to different parts of India and in their turn, built up active centres of research. We, in the South of India are indirect beneficiaries of the school of chemistry developed by the Acharya at Calcutta; Prof. B. B. Dey was one of his students and many of you are aware of the great role he played in the cause of chemical education in South India.

May the great Acharya's life and achievements continue to inspire us and the coming generations.

I have chosen to talk today about a subject viz, base-catalysed rearrangements of oxy-Cope systems, to which, we in the Madras University believe, we made the earliest contributions though work in the area has received a greater impetus since 1975, thanks to the efforts of Evans and Golob in U.S.A.

An oxy-Cope system is a 3-hydroxy-1,5-hexadiene system of the type (1). In the presence of a base, it may rearrange to an enol of the type (2a) or (2b), which gives after protonation carbonyl compounds of the type (2c) or (2d). The rearrangement of

1 to 2c is a [3,3]sigmatropic rearrangement whereas the rearrangement of 1 to 2d is a [1,3]sigmatropic rearrangement. The end products (2c) and (2d) will be different if the system (1) is suitably substituted. The rearrangements may be concerted as indicated above; in such a case the [3,3]rearrangement is usually

referred to as anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement. The rearrangement may also involve a fragmentation-recombination mechanism as follows:

Compound (2c) or (2d) will result depending on whether the Michael addition takes place at C₄ or C₆.

In fact the first example of a base catalyzed rearrangement of an oxy-Cope system reported from the author's laboratory was rationalized as a fragmentation-recombination reaction. It relates to the rearrangement of the vinyl carbinol (3) to the ring enlarged diketone (4). The carbon atoms C₁₀, C₉, C₁, C_{8a}, C_{4a} and C₅ with an -OH at C₁ constitute the oxy-Cope moiety present in 3.

This example also antedates the introduction of the term oxy-Cope rearrangement by Berson² in 1964 to describe the [3,3]sigmatropic rearrangement of systems of the type (5) under neutral conditions².

² The first example of an oxy-Cope (and Cope) rearrangement documented in literature appears to be the thermal conversion of diallyl glycols of the type (i) to substituted cyclopentene aldehydes (ii) reported by M. Urien, *Ann. Chimie*, 1934, 1, 5.

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Substrate (5) and related oxy-Cope substrates of the type used by Berson have recently been shown by Evans and Golob³ to rearrange much faster as alkoxides (6) formed in the presence of metal hydrides in ionising solvents or by complexing agents. As contrasted with these systems, the bicyclic substrate (3) and related systems studied in the author's laboratory contain a carbonyl group conjugated with the terminal olefinic carbon atom remote from the anionic centre. This additional structural feature is believed to delocalize the anionic charge and to cause a switch to the ionic mechanism first proposed¹ for the conversion of carbinol (3) to diketone (4).

Scope of the rearrangements

The rearrangement irrespective of the mechanism involved, is proving to be a versatile reaction especially since the contribution by Evans and Golob³ for the synthesis of a variety of carbon skeletons. The substrates incorporating an oxy-Cope moiety which have been studied fall into the following categories :

- (A). Bicyclo-1,2-condensed systems of the type (3) which give two carbon ring expansion products and which undergo in some cases transannular reactions.
- (B). Bridged systems of the type (5) which lead to *cis* fused octalenones of the type (7).
- (C). Spiro systems.
- (D). Aromatic systems.
- (E). Monocyclic and acyclic systems.

A. *Bicyclo-1,2-condensed systems and two carbon ring expansions :*

The base catalysed rearrangement of the carbinol (3) to the ring enlarged dione (4) came to light during attempts to effect allylic rearrangement of 3.

In these studies¹, the epimeric carbinols (3) and (3a) [and their acetates (3b) and (3c)] were treated with catalytic or equivalent amounts of potassium hydroxide in aqueous methanol and the isomeric product (4) resulted. The structure of 4 was originally deduced from its light absorptions and confirmed later by conversion to the known methyl benzocyclooctene (8) and by dehydrogenation to the phenol (9) which was synthesized independently.

The formation of the diketone (4) from the carbinol (3) or (3a) involving an expansion of a six membered ring to an eight membered ring was rationalized as an initial C₁-C_{8a} bond cleavage followed by an intramolecular Michael type addition and finally an isomerization to the more stable enedione (4). The conversion of the diacetate (3b) or (3c) to dione (4) must involve an initial saponifi-

cation of the parent carbinol. The α -acetylenic precursor (10) of 3 also undergoes rearrangement to give the diene dione (11), though in poorer yield. In these rearrangements the olefinic carbon C₈ is a

key atom involved not only in the formation of the eight membered ring but also in the equilibration of the initially formed dione. Substitution at this position did not alter⁵ or hinder the course of rearrangement and carbinols (12) and (13) furnished the diones (14) and (15) respectively when treated with methanolic potassium hydroxide. The acetylene-

precursors (16) and (17) however, gave under the same conditions the acids (18) and (19), respectively formed by cleavage of the rearranged products. The rearrangement occurred with the

carbinol (20) which afforded the bicyclo(4,5,0) undecane derivative (21) and also with the carbinol (22) which furnished⁶ the dione (23). Both the

carbinols (3) and (12) have been found to undergo rearrangement, though much less readily, by simply refluxing in a high boiling solvent to give dione (4) and (14), respectively. For the base catalyzed conversion of 3 to 4 a concerted Cope mechanism^{5,7} was also considered.

In experiments conducted under mild conditions (room temp. and dil. alkali), 3 and 10 furnished⁷ the rearranged carbinols (24) and (25), respectively in 15 and 10% yields, respectively in addition to the dione (4) and (11).

The carbinols (24) and (25) were found to rearrange readily to 4 and 11 on heating with methanolic potassium hydroxide. The product (24) is believed to be a kinetic product of protonation formed via the alkoxide (26) by an internal 1,2-addition followed by isomerization and protonation rather than as an intermediate in the conversion of 3 to 4. The formation of 25 has also been rationa-

lised similarly. Photochemically, 3 and 10 rearrange⁸ to the β,γ -unsaturated ketones (27) and (28), which under controlled conditions isomerise to the conjugated enones (25) and (24), respectively.

Extension^{9a,9b} of the above studies to the bicyclo oxy-Cope system (29) has shown that a transannular reaction occurs in addition to the rearrangement to give the tricyclic^b product (30). The oxy-Cope system

present in compound (31) also undergoes¹⁰ rearrangement followed by a transannular reaction to give^b the bicyclo (2,2,2) octane derivative, (32)^c. The system

(36) has also been found to rearrange¹¹ in the presence of base to the bicyclo (2,2,1) heptane derivative (37).

An entirely original route^{12a,b} to the hydrazulene dione (39) is based on the rearrangement of the bicyclo (3,3,0) substrate (38).

^b The tricyclic skeleton of 30 is present in retigeranic acid, a sesterpene and also in isocomena, a sesquiterpene.

^c The tricyclic skeleton of 32 is present in patchouli alcohol and seychellene.

Recently, Tice and Heathcock^{1,4} have studied the base catalyzed rearrangement of the enone alcohol (40). Product (41) or its isomer (42) is obtained depending on whether potassium hydride in tetrahydrofuran or methanolic potassium hydroxide is

used as base. They have rationalised their results as indicated in Scheme-1. They invoke⁵ the formation of epimeric alkoxide (44) which they believe is more prone to suffer an oxy-Cope rearrangement to give 45 which is protonated in a protic medium irreversibly. However, in aprotic media (KH in THF) 45 equilibrates as shown with 43 which undergoes an aldol closure on the α -carbon of the dienolate systems to provide 46 which in turn goes to 47 by an oxy-Cope path. An equilibration of 47 followed by

Scheme 1

an internal Michael addition leads to 49, the enolate of the tricyclic dione (41). Both 41 and 42 can be formed directly by Michael reactions of 43 as has been suggested for the rearrangement of 3, 31, etc. The authors consider this pathway as less likely particularly for the diketone (42) where an eight-membered ring is formed.

B. Rearrangement of bridged oxy-Cope systems :

Reference has already been made to the rearrangement of the bridged oxy-Cope system (5) first reported² by Berson and Jones under neutral conditions. This rearrangement was brought about by heating 50 and 5 at 320° in vapour phase. Under the same conditions the epimer (53) gave only ketones (55) and (56); compound (54) also behaved likewise. The 50→51 transformation is an example

of [3,3]sigmatropic shift leading to an enol followed by ketonization. Recently Evans and Golob reported³ that the rearrangement 5→52 is dramatically accelerated by an alkoxide substituent e.g. when OH is replaced by OK. The potassium

alkoxide (57) underwent rearrangement within several minutes at 66° and after quenching with water gave the methoxy ketone (52) in 98% yield. Quantitatively, the rate of rearrangement of 57 was 10¹² times the rate of parent alcohol (5). Such rate accelerations have been reported¹⁵⁻¹⁷ for 58 and 59 also.

A clear trend was seen in going from covalent to more highly ionized salts (K > Na > Li). The rearrangement was also accelerated by highly ionizing solvents (HMPA > THF > ether) and by complexing agents (18-crown-6 or 15-crown-5).

Anionic 1,3-oxy-Cope rearrangements :

The same effect has been observed also in 1,3-oxy-Cope rearrangements. For example, the system (60) undergoes¹⁸ a two-carbon ring expansion to give the eleven membered compound (61) under neutral conditions when heated. This rearrangement is

accelerated considerably by an alkoxide substituent and occurs at room temp.¹⁹. The major product

(63) results from a 1,3-shift with retention of double bond geometry. The minor products (64) and (65) result from loss of *cis* geometry and [3,3]sigmatropic shift, respectively. This has utilized²⁰ the 1,3-rearrangement to develop a new route to benzo condensed medium rings.

The lithium salt of (66) has available both 3,3- and 1,3-rearrangement pathways; only the 3,3-shift occurs²¹ leading to the product (66a).

Geometrical requirements :

Interestingly, the epimer of 57 (57a) which is geometrically precluded from reaction by a concerted 3,3-shift does not rearrange when refluxed with potassium hydroxide in THF though it could rearrange by a 1,3-shift. Presumably, it is easier to bring the ends of the *bis* allyl system of a 1,2-dialkenyl cycloalkane where the alkenyl groups are in a *cis* rather than a *trans* relationship. In general, the *cis* and *trans* configurations may be said to be respectively favourable and unfavourable to oxy-Cope rearrangements. However Mukai *et al*²² have reported [1,3], [1,5] and [3,3]sigmatropic rearrangements of 1,5,5'- and antibisallylic 1,5,7-triene alkoxydes (67 and 68) incorporated within the homotropilidenes (69) and (70), respectively. These carbinols rearrange quantitatively to 4-hydroxytricyclo(5,3,2,0^{4,8})dodeca-2,9,11-triene (71) when heated with sodium hydride in tetrahydrofuran. Surprisingly the anti alkoxydes (70) (M=Na or K) rearranged to 71 much faster than 69 to 71. This facile rearrangement is the first example reported in the literature

of an epimerically unfavourable anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement.

C. Rearrangement in spiro systems :

The spiro oxy-Cope system (72) gives rise¹⁸ to the phenalene dione (74) when treated with methanolic base. The formation of the dione (74) must involve a fragmentation-recombination mechanism involving species (73a) or a concerted mechanism involving species (73b) followed by appropriate isomerization, Michael additions and protonation.

In an approach²³ to the synthesis of the antibiotic pleuromutilin, the model spiro oxy system (75) has been rearranged (KH, THF) to the bridged

eight membered compound (76). Bicyclic bridged olefins of the type (76) in which ring A is varied have been synthesised²⁴ similarly from other spirocyclic precursors.

D. Rearrangements in aromatic systems :

Substrates derived from 1,2-quinones also undergo the anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement²⁵. For example, the *trans* divinyl carbinol (77) derived from 9,10-phenanthroquinone when refluxed with KH in THF gives the dibenzotropone (78) probably formed as indicated. The carbinol (79) undergoes rearrangement to give the benzotropone (80) rather than (81). In the case of both the carbinols (77) and (79), the vinyl moieties must be pseudoequatorial to bring their ends within bonding distance.

A rearrangement in which one of the double bonds of the oxy-Cope moiety is an aromatic double bond, termed an aromatic oxy-Cope rearrangement, has been realised^{26b} under anionic conditions. The naphthyl carbinol (88a) rearranges in the presence of potassium hydride in HMPA to give in low yield (10%) the [3,3]sigmatropic shift product (88c); the 1,3-shift product (88b) is the major product (57%). The phenyl carbinol (88d) under

the same condition, however, gives a 1,3-shift pro-

duct (88e) exclusively. Two other examples^{30,31} of aromatic oxy-Cope rearrangements in the presence of base leading to natural products are referred to later.

E. Rearrangements in homocyclic and acyclic systems :

Some examples of such rearrangements have already been referred to earlier (under B) ; further examples of rearrangements in homocyclic systems are referred to later in the section dealing with the utility of the anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement for syntheses of natural products.

The syntheses and anionic oxy-Cope rearrangements of 1,2-dialkenylcyclobutanols have been

reported³² by Gadwood and Lett. Treatment of the carbinols (89) with KH/THF induced rearrangements to Z and E cyclooctenones (89a) and (89b),

respectively. The alkenyl groups in the starting carbinols are believed to be *trans* ; a fragmentation of the corresponding alkoxides followed by reclosure is assumed to give the *cis* geometry necessary for the rearrangement to occur.

An efficient eight-carbon ring expansion has been reported³³ when the carbinol (96) is treated with

KH/THF. The reaction is believed to proceed by path A involving an unprecedented vinylogous oxy-Cope rearrangement or path B involving consecutive [3,3]sigmatropic shifts.

The divinyl carbinols (97a) and (97b) undergo rearrangement³⁴ to the angularly methylated octalins (98a) and (98b), respectively. These conver-

sions must undoubtedly involve a base catalysed oxy-Cope rearrangement followed by transannular aldol condensation as pictured below :

Mechanism

The mechanism of the anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement depends apparently on whether the substrate undergoing the rearrangement has a carbonyl group conjugated with the double bond away from the anionic centre as in the case of 3 or does not have such a group as in the case of 5 and related systems. Evans and Nelson have recently³⁵ provided elegant

proof that the rearrangement proceeds in a concerted fashion in systems of the type (82a) and (82b) which fall into the second category. They synthesised the two sets of diastereo isomeric dienols, (82a), (82b) and (83a), (83b) and found that dienols (82a) and (83b) afforded only ketones in set I and that dienols (82b) and (83a) afforded those in set II.

The non-occurrence of more than two ketone products or a combination of any two products from sets I and II is indeed quite striking and rules out unequivocally any non-concerted or stepwise mechanism for rearrangement of the above type of substrates. In the rearrangements of all four dienols the product ratios were found to be as follows :

Substrates	Product composition			
	84t	85c	84c	85t
82a	96	4	< 1	≤ 1
83b	30	70	< 1	< 1
82b	≤ 1	≤ 1	77	23
83a	< 1	0-2	2-0	98

In the rearrangements of all the four dienols, chair transition states are preferred. This preference is almost exclusive in the case of dienols (82a) and (83a) and less so in the case of dienols (82b) and

(83b). The chair and boat transition states for 82a and 82b are C₁ and B₁ whereas for 83b and 83a these are C₂ and B₂. The diastereomer (82b)

with 'pseudoaxial -OMe (R₁ = OMe, R₂ = H) should be more destabilised than 82a (R₁ = H, R₂ = OMe), thus accounting for the 77 : 23 ratio of products as contrasted with 96 : 4 ratio of the products in the case of 82a. Likewise for diastereomers (83a) and (83b), the same destabilising factor as applied to C₂ can explain the product ratios.

For conjugated oxy-Cope systems of the type (3), critical evidence has been obtained recently which indicates that the rearrangement is concerted when carried out with KH/THF and stepwise or non-concerted with NaOMe/MeOH or KOH/MeOH. Uma³⁵ has synthesised the optically active ethynyl and vinyl carbinols (85) and (86), respectively from the optically active dione (84) and studied their rearrangements (Scheme 2).

Uma finds that the acetylenic carbinol (85) rearranges in the presence of KH/THF to give *ca* 80% yield of the crystalline dione (87) with $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 292.8^\circ$ whereas with 0.2% NaOMe in CH₃OH, it gives racemic dione (87) also in about 80% yield as a pale yellow liquid with identical ir, uv and pmr absorptions. The optically active vinyl carbinol (86) when treated with KH/THF gives two isomeric liquid products, each in 30% yield and each optically active. The product with $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 18.2^\circ$ is found to be optically active (88) whereas the other products

with $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 24^\circ$ is either (89a) or (89b). On the other hand, the optically active vinyl carbinol (86) when treated with KOH/MeOH furnishes only the racemic dione (86). Though the optical purity of 87 and 88 is yet to be determined, the above results

Scheme 2

are best rationalised as shown below :

The retention of optical activity undoubtedly supports the concerted mechanism 'a' in the non-protic medium for the formation to a definite extent of the ketone (88) [and (87)]; the total racemization observed in the case of the protic medium indicates the fragmentation-recombination mechanism 'b'. Other subtle mechanistic aspects of the above rearrangement are under study in the author's laboratory.

Synthetic utility of base catalyzed oxy-Cope rearrangement

The increased yields and the lower reaction temperatures in base catalyzed oxy-Cope processes have established their utility in the syntheses of some natural products and analogues. These include (i) the synthesis of a norsteroid²⁷, by rearrangement of compound (90) in which the aromatic ring

provides an olefinic component, (ii) the synthesis of coronofac acid²⁸ from an intermediate obtained by a similar rearrangement of the oxy-Cope system (91), (iii) the synthesis²⁹ of (\pm) erythro juvabione (92), a sesquiterpene from the mixture of ketones (82a) and (82b), (iv) the synthesis²⁹ of the nitrogenous base (93), (v) the synthesis^{17a} of some germacrane (medium ring sesquiterpenes) and a new approach to the synthesis^{17b} of germacrane skeleton and (vi) the synthesis³⁰ of the precursor (95) for prostoglandins by the rearrangement of the secondary carbinol (94).

A new synthesis³¹ of (4,4,4)-propallane (96) also involves the use of an anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement. The base catalyzed rearrangements of oxy-Cope systems will play a greater role in future syntheses of natural products and also other products with complex structures.

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